

POWER OUTAGE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON VALUE CHAIN ALONG ABA AND ITU NATIONAL GRID OF UYO AND EKET METROPOLITAN CITIES IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

The study was set to tackle and proffer solution to the recurrent power outages usually witnessed along Aba and Itu National Grid that threw the entire Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities and their environs into total blackout thereby, impacting gross negative implications on the socio-economic development of the entire areas. Two theories were adopted to frame the study, namely: The Fluid Theories of Electricity and the Porter's Value Chain Theory. The methodology used in this research was the Descriptive Survey design. The population consisted of 1,329,000 PHED customers who are indigenes and occupants of the Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities. The methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. Three subsidiary objectives were set, among others, was to find the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis. A well-developed Likert-type scale was used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentage tables. The hypothesis was tested using the inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) at 0.05 level of significance. The results obtained showed that, there are gross negative implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses as well as individuals in Uyo and Eket metropolis. The three recommendations based on the foregoing, were also put forward to resolve the issues found in the study. Among them was that, the Federal Government should accept the fact that there are gross negative implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses as well as individuals in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to the incessant and recurrent power outages on the Aba and Itu

National Grid. As such, federal government should equip and provide favorable conditions that would enable PHED to carry out effective and efficient service delivery to the people.

Keywords: Power outage, Implications, Value chain, Cosmopolitan cities, National Grid.

1. Introduction

A power outage (also called a power-cut, a power out, a power failure, a power blackout, a power loss, or a blackout) is the loss of the electrical power network supply to an end user. There are many causes of power failures in an electricity network. Examples of these causes include faults at power stations, damage to electric transmission lines, substations or other parts of the distribution system, a short circuit, cascading failure, fuse or circuit breaker operation.

Power failures are particularly critical at sites where the environment and public safety are at risk. Institutions such as hospitals, sewage treatment plants, and mines will usually have backup power sources such as standby generators, which will automatically start up when electrical power is lost. Other critical systems, such as telecommunication, are also required to have emergency power. The battery room of a telephone exchange usually has arrays of lead-acid batteries for backup and also a socket for connecting a generator during extended periods of outage.

The problem of electricity in Nigeria, as a whole, dates back to her independence in 1960. Successive governments (both democratic and the military governments) have variously tackled this problem of electricity generation and distribution so much in this country, yet it still seems as though not enough efforts have been put in that direction. No new government has ever emerged in Nigeria without making several promises during campaigns, on how it intends to tackle the problem of electricity/power outage in the country.

The researchers are compelled by the recurrent power outages recently witnessed along Aba and Itu national grid that had thrown the entire metropolitan cities of Uyo and Eket, and their environs into total blackout thereby impacted greatly on the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State. First, it happened in the middle of May, 2023 and, second it occurred between Tuesday, 27th and ended in the evening of Friday, 30th June, 2023.

Thereafter, it had become a recurrent decimal in this particular grid under investigation. It is therefore, the intention of the researchers to use the aforementioned towns, Uyo and Eket to generally find out how the recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid had disrupted value chain on the above mentioned cosmopolitan cities of Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of electricity in Nigeria, as a whole, dates back to her independence in 1960. Successive governments (both democratic and the military governments) have variously tackled this problem of electricity generation and distribution so much in this country, yet it still seems as though not enough efforts have been put in that direction. No new government has ever emerged in Nigeria without making several promises during campaigns, on how it intends to tackle the problem of electricity in the country. The researchers are compelled by the recurrent power outages recently experienced along Aba and Itu national grid which had thrown the entire metropolitan cities of Uyo and Eket, and their environs into total blackout thereby impacted greatly on the socio-economic development of the above mentioned cosmopolitan cities in Akwa Ibom State.

This topic is intended to be treated under this condition, in four dimensions, as the problems surrounding value chain during power outage, have been identified. This include: the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses (SMEs); implications of value chain on private and family lives; implications of value chain on personal independence; and, implications of value chain on security and citizens' night lives.

Having stated the obvious, let's begin with the first dimension which is the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses. A problem on the national grid is a problem on the entire sphere of operation of such grid. A problem on the national grid is a total black out on a large spectrum of area, in and around the location of the problem to as far as the extent of its coverage. Lately, it has been observed that the Aba and Itu national grid has been faced with incessant power outages to the extent the entire Uyo metropolis, as well as Eket and their environs were thrown into total black out during these periods, for a number of days before the problem was rectified.

First, it happened in the middle of May, 2023 and, second it occurred between Tuesday, 27" and ended in the evening of Friday, 30 June, 2023. Chances are

that the incident may occur again and again, except permanent solution is found. This incident might have occurred as a result of the heavy rain that fell almost uninterruptedly in parts of the state from Tuesday, 27th up to Thursday, 29th June, 2023. This incident has caused the state a serious set-back in terms of its socio-economic development.

For example, the situation has brought untold hardship on the citizenry and on the masses, particularly, the electricity users; small and medium scale businesses (SMEs) which drive the bulk of the societal economy were seriously slowed down or temporarily folded up. Before now, almost every business was able to switch on its private generating set to power its business premises in event of power failure. But, in recent times, due to the high cost of premium motor spirit also known as petrol, which is caused by the recent subsidy removal by the Tinubu-led federal government on May 31, this year most businesses run serious losses in buying fuel to run their generators and provide the same services hitherto provided for their customers. At the end of the scenario, it is the customers that bear the final burden of paying higher for the services they received. Furthermore, such other small and medium scale businesses like commodity shops, barber/hair dressing saloons, laundry/dry cleaning shops, phones/laptops charging stations; other business centers for internet operations, typing, photocopying, scanning and lamination; printing press; private schools; and, hotels, etc. that should move the economy of the state forward on a day-to-day basis were stalled, slowed down or temporarily closed down because of lack of electricity.

The implications of value chain on private/family lives. A particular attention is on the private and family lives of the citizens of the state in the two cosmopolitan town, Uyo and Eket as mentioned earlier on, which were observed during the period under study to have been seriously jeopardized. It was observed that many private homes were no longer able to afford petrol to power their generators, due to the high cost of the commodity. The few that still maintain their status quo only manage to do so. Some families commit almost their entire monthly earnings or family business finances into providing electricity in their homes. Others who cannot afford to purchase the highly expensive petrol to run their generators no longer enjoy fans and air conditioners. Their homes are devoid of good ventilation. As such, they suffer heat, especially during the dry season. Excessive heat, in turn can cause some health challenges like heat rashes, dehydration, draught, soar-throat, etc.

Also in such homes, their food stuff and cooked foods, especially soups could easily get spoiled as their refrigerators and deep freezers no longer function due to lack of electricity. Another major challenge of the value chain on the private homes is the issue of water. Of course, it is often said that, "water is life". As most families depend on their private water supply, most of them during those periods of power outage, struggled to pump water from their boreholes due to high cost of fuel or diesel. Those who insist kept depleting their family income. But those families that cannot afford to run their private generators to power their systems, are thrown into what the authors call, "new dependency".

The implications of value chain on independence: This factor has caused many citizens who had managed to self-sufficient, self-reliant and independent to be thrown back to what the authors call, "new dependency". By new dependency, it means that some citizens who were capable of taking care of themselves and their families were compelled by the current realities to seek to have new friends in the neighbourhood who were could help to charge their phones, laptops and other rechargeable instruments in the neighbours' houses for them because the friends are able to provide alternative source of power unlike them. The implication is that dependency being what it is (whether old or new), it would not allow for rapid growth and development of individual and society.

The implications of value chain on safety and security and night lives of citizens. The safety of the lives and property of Nigerians at this time can no longer be guaranteed. This is because of the recent pronouncement by President Asiwaju Bola Tinubu on the removal of fuel subsidy has caused a sudden and an uncontrollable economic crisis in the country. Apart from the independent fuel marketers taking over the economy and selling fuel at exorbitant and uncontrollable prices. This situation has caused a sudden and unabated proliferation of black market trading in the country. In all major roads, streets, corners and junctions in all cities and villages today in Nigeria, are found these hawkers selling fuel between N600.00 and N750.00, depending on what part of the country that you are buying the product.

On the other hand, it is common knowledge that crimes thrive more in the cover of darkness than they do in the broad day light. During those periods of power outages under study, there were cases of pickpocketing, snatching of hand bags and phones from unsuspecting passers by mostly at Uyo By-pass as well as at Itam Flyover and Akpan Andem Market. Some keke drivers were also reported to have rubbed some of their passengers as they drove them pass their

bus stop to unknown destinations without their knowledge due to darkness on the road. Security lights along the Goodluck Jonathan Bullavat (the new stadium road) in particular, were removed as the whole of that area was dark, due to lack of electricity in the town.

The new ring road, from the newly constructed round about at Aka Road down to the Water Fountain at Oron Road in Uyo metropolis was a safe haven for criminals to operate unchallenged from about 7.00 pm upward. Cases of car snatches were reported at Atiku Abubakar Flyover at about 7.00pm during the period. Several incidents of criminal activities were also reported to have taken place in Eket town during that period, particularly in and around Grace Bill and the re-modelling environments. There were cases of bags and phones snatches from unsuspecting public.

Finally, the night lives of the citizens were at risk as hoodlums had a fair deal in the streets under the cover of darkness. The usual business environment like, Maitama in Ewet Housing Estate and other seat outs and eateries were operating at skeletal level. Most people were afraid to leave their houses at night to go out, while those who left homes since day time hastened back before getting late. Finally, as night clubs, seat outs and eateries powered their drinks to be cold with their plants, so also were prices of drinks raised. For instance, Champion and 33 Export Larger Beer were raised from N400.00 and 500.00, the initial prices, respectively to 500.00 and 600.00 per bottle, respectively in some seat outs in Uyo and Eket. The prices might not have returned after the restoration of light in the city.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to find out how the recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid had disrupted value chain on some cosmopolitan cities in Akwa Ibom State. The subsidiary objectives are:

- i. To find out the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket Metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid.
- ii. To determine the implications of value chain on private/family lives of citizens in Uyo and Eket Metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid.
- iii. To examine the implications of value chain on the people of Uyo and Eket metropolis on their independence due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid.
- iv. To ascertain government awareness of the implications of value chain

on security and night lives of citizens in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid..

Research Questions

Based on the above research objectives, the following questions were asked in order to elicit answers from respondents.

- i. What are the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid?
- ii. What are the implications of value chain on private/family lives of the people in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid?
- iii. What are the implications of value chain on the people of Uyo and Eket metropolis on their independence due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid?
- iv. What is government awareness on the implications of value chain on security and night lives of the people in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid?

Research Hypotheses

The research postulated one composite null (H) in order carry out scientific and empirical verifications on the above research questions:

H₀: There are no significant implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid.

Literature Review

The Concept of Power Outage

A power outage (also called a power-cut, a power out, a power failure, a power blackout, a power loss, or a blackout) is the loss of the electrical power network supply to an end user. There are many causes of power failures in an electricity network. Examples of these causes include faults at power stations, damage to electric transmission lines, substations or other parts of the distribution system, a short circuit, cascading failure, fuse or circuit breaker operation.

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and mines will usually have backup power sources such as standby generators, which will automatically start up when electrical power is lost. Other critical systems, such as telecommunication, are also required to have emergency power. The battery room of a telephone exchange usually has arrays of lead-acid batteries for backup and also a socket for connecting a generator during extended periods of outage.

Types of Power Outage

Power outages are categorized into three different phenomena, relating to the duration and effect of the outage. These include: Transient fault, Black out and Rolling Blackout.

i. Transient fault:

A transient fault is a loss of power typically caused by a fault on a power line, e.g. a short circuit or flashover. Power is automatically restored once the fault is cleared. A brownout is a drop in voltage in an electrical power supply. The term brownout comes from the dimming experienced by incandescent lighting when the voltage sags. Brownouts can cause poor performance of equipment or even incorrect operation. Outages may last from a few minutes to a few weeks depending on the nature of the blackout and the configuration of the electrical network.

ii. Blackout

A blackout is the total loss of power to a wider area and of long duration. It is the most severe form of power outage that can occur. Blackouts which result from or result in power stations tripping are particularly difficult to recover from quickly.

Rolling blackouts

Rolling blackouts occur when demand for electricity exceeds supply, and allow some customers to receive power at the required voltage at the expense of other customers who get no power at all. They are a common occurrence in developing countries, and may be scheduled in advance or occur without warning. They have also occurred in developed countries, for example in the California electricity crisis of 2000-2001, when government deregulation destabilized the wholesale electricity market. Blackouts are also used as a public safety measure, such as to prevent a gas leak from catching fire (for example, power was cut to several towns in response to the Merrimack Valley gas explosions), or to prevent wildfires around poorly maintained transmission lines (such as during the 2019 California power shutoffs).

Protecting the Power System from Outages

Tree limbs creating a short circuit in power lines during a storm. This typically results in a power outage in the area supplied by these lines. In power supply networks, the power generation and the electrical load (demand) must be very close to equal every second to avoid overloading of network components, which can severely damage them. Protective relays and fuses are used to automatically detect overloads and to disconnect circuits at risk of damage. Under certain conditions, a network component shutting down can cause current fluctuations in neighboring segments of the network leading to a cascading failure of a larger section of the network. This may range from a building, to a block, to an entire city, to an entire electrical grid.

Modern power systems are designed to be resistant to this sort of cascading failure, but it may be unavoidable (see below). Moreover, since there is no short-term economic benefit to preventing rare large-scale failures, researchers have expressed concern that there is a tendency to erode the resilience of the network over time, which is only corrected after a major failure occurs. In a 2003 publication, Carreras and co-authors claimed that reducing the likelihood of small outages only increases the likelihood of larger ones. In that case, the short-term economic benefit of keeping the individual customer happy increases the likelihood of large-scale blackouts.

The Senate Committee on Energy and Natural Resources held a hearing in October, 2018 to examine "black start", the process of restoring electricity after a system-wide power loss. The hearing's purpose was for Congress to learn about what the backup plans are in the electric utility industry in the case that the electric grid is damaged. Threats to the electrical grid include cyber attacks, solar storms, and severe weather, among others. For example, the "Northeast Blackout of 2003" was caused when overgrown trees touched high-voltage power lines. Around 55 million people in the U.S. and Canada lost power, and restoring it cost around \$6 billion.

Restoring Power After a Wide-area Outage

Restoring power after a wide-area outage can be difficult, as power stations need to be brought back online. Normally, this is done with the help of power from the rest of the grid. In the total absence of grid power, a so-called black start needs to be performed to bootstrap the power grid into operation. The means of doing so will depend greatly on local circumstances and operational policies, but typically transmission utilities will establish localized 'power islands' which are then progressively coupled together. To maintain supply

frequencies within tolerable limits during this process, demand must be reconnected at the same pace that generation is restored, requiring close coordination between power stations, transmission and distribution organizations.

Overview of Electricity Sector

Electricity generation began in Nigeria at the end of the 19th century with the installation of the first generating power plant in Lagos. By 1950, the colonial government passed the Ordinance No. 15 of 1950 and established a unified body referred to as Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN) to integrate all the government and native owned generation plants and their transmission and distribution systems. Also, the Niger Dams Authority (NDA) was set up in 1961 to manage and exploit the hydropower potentials of the country.

However, the ECN and NDA was merged in 1972 to form a single entity known as National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) mandated to develop and maintain a co-ordinated, reliable power supply in the country. NEPA was managed in a top down vertically integrated model with full scale monopoly in the electricity sector as providers of generation, transmission, distribution and sales to consumers. From 1972 to 2005, NEPA controlled 94% of the generation capacity and 100% of transmission, distribution and marketing of the sector. The network coverage and generation rate grew within the period under the operation of NEPA. For instance, the number of states in the country with access to electricity increased from eight (8) in 1983 to 36 in 2003 and the energy generated rose from 8,456GWH to 22,612GWH within the stated period (Adoghe et al, 2008).

Despite this leap, the over-centralization of the utility coupled with poor maintenance, economic mismanagement of the utility, inadequate power supply due to under-investment and dilapidated infrastructures to meet the growing population was worrisome Graph 1 below shows the level of funding by the Federal Government for PHCN operations in the power sector from 1974 to 2003. It is reported that during the military rule (1989-1999), no new generating plan was added to the grid. For instance, Adogamhe (2012) estimated the cost of unreliable power supply to the Nigeria economy to be about US\$1billion annually. According to World Bank estimates, Nigeria's electricity consumption per capita is rated among the lowest in the World and it has a very high disparity between electricity demand and supply. For example, the electricity generating capacity in Nigeria is about 3,800megawatts (MW) for a 150million population. In comparison with a fellow African country,

South Africa generates over 40,000MW for its 50million people. Graph 2 below shows estimates of different countries generating capacity in relation to its population.

An Overview of Privatization of Power Sector

Electric power came to Nigeria in 1898 with the establishment of the first generating plant by the British colonial government (Okoro & Chikuni, 2007 in Okolobah & Ismail, 2013). The management of the generating plant was named the Public Works Department (PWD). Thereafter, the then Federal Government of Nigeria passed an ordinance in 1950, establishing the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN) saddled with the responsibility of generating, transmitting, distributing and sale of electricity in Nigeria. Other bodies like the Native Authorities and the Nigeria Electricity Supply Company (NESCO) had licenses to produce electricity in some locations in Nigeria (Okobolo & Ismail, 2013).

In 1962, the Federal Government by an act of Parliament established the Niger Dam Authority (NDA). The authority was responsible for the construction and maintenance of dams and other works in the River Niger and elsewhere, generate electricity by water power, improve navigation and promote fisheries and irrigation. The electricity produced by NDA is being sold to ECN for distribution and sales at utility voltages. In April 1972, by a decree, Electricity Corporation of Nigeria and Niger Dam Authority were merged to form National Electric Power Authority (NEPA). The reasons given for this merger include: vesting of production and distribution in one company and that it will bring about more efficient utilization of the human, financial and other resources available to the electricity supply industry in the country (Babatunde, & Shaibu, 2008).

In 1973, NEPA became operational and was responsible for generating, transmitting and distributing of electricity to all parts of the federation. Starting with only four power stations namely Ijora, Delta, Afam thermal stations and Kainji hydro power station with a total installed capacity of 532.6MW serving more than two million customers, which has grown to 5,958MW in year 2000 with the establishment of additional power stations namely Jebba, Shiroro hydro power station Egbin, Sapele, Delta thermal power station in the early eighties having a combined installed generating capacity of 2940MW (PHCN, 2010. Nigeria @ 50: Status of Power sector). In 1988 NEPA was partially commercialized supported by an upward review of the tariffs. This was aimed at attracting investors to the sector. Due to increase in the population of the

country and the absence of additional power plants the available facilities became overstretched and this led to the reform of the power sector.

The Concept of Value Chain

A value chain, as it already been stated, is a progression of activities that a firm operating in a specific industry performs in order to deliver a valuable product (i.e., good and/or service) to the end customer (Petermann et al, 2011). The concept comes through business management and was first described by Michael Porter in his 1985 best-seller, *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. The authors averse that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in society.

The idea of the value chain is based on the process view of organizations, the idea of seeing a manufacturing (or service) organization as a system, made up of subsystems each with inputs, transformation processes and outputs. Inputs, transformation processes, and outputs involve the acquisition and consumption of resources money, labour, materials, equipment, buildings, land, administration and management. How value chain activities are carried out determines costs and affects profits.

According to the OECD Secretary-General (Gurria, 2012) the emergence of global value chains (GVCs) in the late 1990s provided a catalyst for accelerated change in the landscape of international investment and trade, with major, far-reaching consequences on governments as well as enterprises (Gurria, 2012).

Michael Porter's Value Chain

The appropriate level for constructing a value chain is the business unit, not division or corporate level. Products pass through a chain of activities in order, and at each activity the product gains some value. The chain of activities gives the products more added value than the sum of added values of all activities. The activity of a diamond cutter can illustrate the difference between cost and the value chain. The cutting activity may have a low cost, but the activity adds much of the value to the end product, since a rough diamond is significantly less valuable than a cut diamond. Typically, the described value chain and the documentation of processes, assessment and auditing of adherence to the process routines are at the core of the quality certification of the business, example, ISO 9001.

A firm's value chain forms a part of a larger stream of activities, which Porter calls a value system. A value system, or an industry value chain, includes the

suppliers that provide the inputs necessary to the firm along with their value chains. After the firm creates products, these products pass through the value chains of distributors (which also have their own value chains), all the way to the customers. All parts of these chains are included in the value system. To achieve and sustain a competitive advantage, and to support that advantage with information technologies, a firm must understand every component of this value system.

Nigeria's National Power Grid: Aba and Itu Case Study

Nigeria's national power grid connects power generation stations to electrical loads throughout the country. It is a system that comprises power generation companies, power distribution companies, and the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN). More than 23 electricity-generating plants are connected to the power grid. While electricity generation and distribution are permitted to be done by private companies, only the federal government serves as the middleman transmitting generated electricity to distribution companies.

The Aba and Itu National Grid which is the focus of this research is one of the 23 electricity-generating plants connected to the Nigeria's National Power Grid. It covers both Abia and part of Akwa Ibom State. For the purpose of this study, the researchers chose to concentrate in Itu which is the part of the National Grid that is responsible for the provision of electricity for both Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities in Akwa Ibom State. Uyo metropolis is the capital of Akwa Ibom State, South South Nigeria. Ibibo is the language spoken in Uyo. It became the capital on September 23, 1987 when Akwa Ibom was created from the former Cross River State. According to the 2006 Nigerian Census, the population of Uyo (including Itu) is 427,873, while the greater urban area, including Uruan, has a population of 554,906. Ibibio is the primary indigenous language.

On the other hand, Eket is the second metropolitan city covered by the Aba and Itu National Grid. Eket is one of the 31 local government areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The name Eket or Ekid also refers to the indigenous ethnic group of the region and to their language. The Eket people use the endonym Ekid for themselves and their language, but Europeans spell and pronounce the name as "Eket". Eket, apart from being a local government area in Akwa Ibom State is one of the three geopolitical zones in the state. The geopolitical zones are, Uyo senatorial district, Ikot Ekpene senatorial district and Eket senatorial district.

The town itself is an industrial city that in recent years has become a conurbation joining together separate villages. The Office of the Surveyor-General of Akwa Ibom State estimates the area of the Eket Local Government Area to be approximately 176.000 square Km while the 2006 National Census gives the population of the Local Government Area as 172,856. However, the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development gives the 2013 estimated population of the Eket Local Government Area as given as 218,438 with a population density of 1,241/square Km.

The reliability of the national power grid has often been questioned. This is not unrelated to the fact that over the past 12 years (2010 to June 2022), the power grid has collapsed 222 times at the minimum. This number takes into consideration both partial and total grid collapse. In 2022, the grid collapsed seven times from January to September 2022. Reasons for the partial and total collapse include grid instability which occurs when demand for electricity does not match its supply; overly volatile loads especially from steel mills; the TCN's weak and old infrastructure; the absence of a majority of the transition lines. In June 2022, protesting electricity workers under the National Union of Electricity Employees (NUEE) engaged in a strike action resulting in a shutdown of the grid, thus causing similar outcomes as when there is a grid collapse. Following a grid collapse incidence, the National Control Centre (NCC) typically works to restore it.

To meet Nigeria's future energy demands, research has established that gas and oil power plants remain the best choice where the country has no GHG reduction commitments. However, considering Nigeria's commitment to the Paris Agreement, the ideal choice is nuclear energy to meet its future energy demands. While renewable energy sources like solar have often been suggested as viable options to provide cleaner off-grid electricity, they are also regarded as insufficient to meet the country's long-term energy needs in the future.

History of Fuel Price Hike in Nigeria

- i. **Gowon:** 1973 6k to 8.45k (40.8%)
- ii. **Murtala:** 1976 8.45k to 9k (0.59%)
- iii. **Obasanjo:** October, 1978 9k to 15.3k (70%)
- iv. **Shagari:** April 20, 1982 15.3k to 20k (30.71%)
- v. **Babangida:** March 31, 1986 20k to 39.5k (97.5%)
- vi. **Babangida:** April 10, 1988 39.5k to 42k (6.33%)
- vii. **Babangida:** January 1, 1989 42k to 60k Private vehicles

- Babangida:** December 19, 1989 Moved to uniform price of 60k (42.86%)
viii. **Babangida:** March 6, 1991 60k to 70k (16.67%)
ix. **Shonekan:** November 8, 1993 70k to N5 (61.4%)
x **Abacha:** November 22, 1993 Petrol price dropped from N5 to N3.25k (361.54%)
xi. Abubakar: December 20, 1998 N11 to N25 (127.27%)
xii. Abubakar: January 6, 1999 N25 to N20 (-20%)
xiii. Obasanjo: January 1, 2002 N22 to N26 (18.18%)
xiv. Obasanjo: June-October, 2003 N26 to N42 (23.08%)
xv. Obasanjo: May 29, 2004 N50 (19.05%)
xvi. Obasanjo: August 25, 2004 N22 to N26 (30%)
xvii. Obasanjo: May 2, 2007 N75 (15.38%)
xviii. Ya'Adua: June, 2007 N65(-15.38%)
xix. Jonathan:
January 1, 2012 B/w N138 and N250 (112.3 to 284.82%)
xx. Tinubu: May 31, 2023
Source: Fuel Regime in Nigeria: Retrieved on 02 July, 2023.

Due to subsidy removal, prices of fuel were determined by Independent Marketers in different states of the federation b/w N488 and N600. In Akwa Ibom State, it was sold at about N535 at the NNPC Mega Station.

Theoretical Framework

This study is adopting the following theories as its theoretical framework. They are the Fluid Theories of Electricity and the Porter's Value Chain Theory.

Fluid Theories of Electricity

Fluid theories of electricity are outdated theories that postulated one or more electrical fluids which were thought to be responsible for many electrical phenomena in the history of electromagnetism. The "two-fluid" theory of electricity, created by Charles Francisco de Cisternay du Fay, postulated that electricity was the interaction between two electrical 'fluids.' An alternate simpler theory was proposed by Benjamin Franklin, called the unitary, or one-fluid, theory of electricity. This theory claimed that electricity was really one fluid, which could be present in excess, or absent from a body, thus explaining its electrical charge. Franklin's theory explained how charges could be dispelled (such as those in Leyden jars) and how they could be passed through a chain of people. The fluid theories of electricity eventually became updated to include the effects of magnetism and electrons (upon their discovery).

Fluid Theories. In the 1700s many physical phenomena were thought of in terms of an aether, which was a fluid that could permeate matter. This idea had been used for centuries, and was the basis of thinking about physical phenomena, such as electricity, as liquids. Other 18th century examples of fluid models are Lavoisier's caloric and the magnetic fluids of Coulomb and Aepinus.

Two-fluid Theory. By the 18th century, one of a few theories explaining observed electrical phenomena was the two-fluid theory. This theory is generally attributed to Charles François de Cisternay du Fay. du Fay's theory suggested that electricity was composed of two liquids, which could flow through solid bodies. One liquid carried a positive charge, and the other a negative charge. When these two liquids came into contact with one another, they would produce a neutral charge. This theory dealt mainly with explaining electrical attraction and repulsion, rather than how an object could be charged or discharged. du Fay observed this while repeating an experiment created by Otto Von Guericke, wherein a thin material, such as a feather or leaf, would repel a charged object after making contact with it. du Fay observed that the "leaf-gold is first attracted by the tube; and acquires an electricity beapproaching it; and of consequence is immediately repelled by it." This seemed to confirm for du Fay that the leaf was being pushed as a 'current' of electricity flowed around and through it. Through further testing, du Fay determined that an object could hold one of two types of electricity, either vitreous or resinous electricity. He found that an object with vitreous electricity would repel another vitreous object, but would be attracted to an object with resinous electricity. Another supporter of the two-fluid theory was Chrisitan Gottlieb Kratzenstein. He speculated also the that electric charges were carried by vortices in these two fluids.

One-fluid Theory. In 1746 William Watson proposed a one-fluid theory. On 11 July 1747 Benjamin Franklin composed a letter in which he outlined his new theory. This is the first record of his theory. Franklin developed this theory mainly concentrating on the charging and discharging of bodies, as opposed to du Fay, who concentrated mainly on electrical attraction and repulsion.

Franklin's theory stated that electricity should be thought of as the movement of a single liquid, as opposed to the interaction between two liquids. A body would show signs of electricity when it held either too much, or too little of this liquid. A neutral object was therefore thought to contain a "normal" amount of this fluid, Franklin also outlined two possible states of electrification, positive

and negative. He argued that a positively charged object would contain too much fluid, while a negatively charged object would contain too little fluid. Franklin was able to apply this thinking by explaining unexplained phenomena of the time, such as the Leyden jar, a basic charge storing device similar to a capacitor. He argued that the wire and inner surface became positively charged, while the outer surface became negatively charged. This caused an imbalance in fluid, and a person touching both portions of the jar allowed the fluid to flow normally. Despite being a simpler theory, it was heavily debated whether electricity was made up of one fluid or two for a century.

Porter's Value Chain Theory

This theory was propounded by Michael Porter in 1985. Michael Porter's value chain is a strategic business planning tool used to identify where competitive advantage arises in your business. It tracks the impact made on a product or service by every process from its start to delivery. The nine main stages of the value chain are grouped together as five primary activities and four support activities. Experts use this to identify how they can improve organizational effectiveness by improving the quality of internal activities. Primary activities include, inbound logistics: This involves the relationships with suppliers and activities required to receive, store and initially process inputs such as raw materials. Operations: The process of manufacturing or creating.

Methodology

The methodology adopted in this research was the Descriptive Survey design. Methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The primary method involved: personal observation and interviews to people considered to be aware of and conversant with the problem at hand as well as the use of questionnaire forms. On the other hand, the secondary method of data collection included: text books, journals, conference papers, government's official publication, newspapers, magazines and the internet.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section focused on data presentation, analysis and discussion on findings. The result of the data gathered from the questionnaires administered were presented and analyzed below. The simple percentage tables were used in presenting the result of data, while chi-square was used to test just the first hypothesis, due to space constraint.

TABLE 1: Analysis of questionnaire administered.

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Returned	382	95.5
Not returned	18	4.5
Total	400	100

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

The table above indicates that out of 400 questionnaires administered to respondents, 382 questionnaires representing 95.5% were returned while 18 questionnaire representing 4.5% were not returned.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	165	43
Female	217	57
Total	382	100

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

The above table shows that 165 respondents representing 43% were male respondents who returned the questionnaire while 217 respondents representing 57% were female respondents who returned the questionnaire.

Table 3: Age Bracket of Respondents

Age Brackets	Frequency	Percentage
Under 20 years	-	-
21 - 25	130	34
26 – 40	100	26
41 – 50	87	23
51 and above	65	17
Total	382	100

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

The table above shows that 130 respondents representing 34% were between the ages of 21 to 25, 100 respondents representing 26% were between the ages of 26 to 40, 87 respondents representing 23% were between the ages of 41 to 50 while respondents representing 17% falls between the ages of 51 and above.

Table 4: Marital Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	183	48
Married	96	25
Widowed	58	15
Divorced	45	12
Total	382	100

Source: *Field Survey, 2023*

The table above show the marital status of respondent 183 (48%) of the respondents were single, 96 (25%) were married, 58 (15%) were widowed, and 45 (12%) were divorced.

Table 5. Level of Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
WAEC/SSCE	78	20
Diploma	72	19
B.Sc.	83	22
MBA/M.Sc.	82	21
Ph.D. and Above	67	18
Total	382	100

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

The table shows the level of education of respondents. WAEC/SSCE 78 (20%), Diploma 72 (19%), B.Sc. 83 (22%), MBA/M.Sc. 82 (21%), Ph.D and above 67 (18%).

Table 6: Religion of Respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Christian	379	99.2
Muslim	3	0.8
Traditionalist	-	-
Total	382	100

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

The table above shows the religion of respondents. 379 respondents representing 99.2% were Christians, while 3 respondents representing 0.8% were Muslims.

Question 1: What are the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis?

Table 7: Respondents View on the implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
Strongly agreed	192	50
Agreed	90	24
Strongly disagreed	70	18
Disagreed	30	8
Total	382	100%

Source: *Field Survey (2023)*

The table shows that 192 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis, 90 respondents representing 24% agreed, 70 respondents representing 18% strongly disagreed while 30 respondents representing 8% disagreed.

Testing of Hypotheses

The chi- square statistical method was used in testing the hypotheses. In calculating the chi-square, the level of significance is given as 0.05

The degree of freedom (df) is calculated as:

$$df = (R-1)(C-1)$$

Number of row minus 1

Number of column minus 1

To calculate the chi square, the following formula is used:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$$

Where X^2 = chi square

fo = observed frequency

fe = expected frequency

\sum = summation

The expected frequency is calculated as

$$E = \text{Row total} \times \text{column total}$$

Grand Total

Rules of Decision

Where the calculated chi-square value is less than critical table value, null hypothesis will be accepted and alternate hypothesis rejected. But, where the calculated chi-square value is greater than the table values, the alternate hypothesis will be accepted, while the null hypothesis will be rejected. The hypothesis tested in this study is just hypothesis one due to space constraint. Data used for testing the hypothesis are obtained from the responses to the questionnaire distributed in the Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities of Akwa Ibom State.

Test of Hypothesis

Ho: There are no significant implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis

Table 1: Responses from Question one

Responses category	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
Male	98	28	47	11	218
Female	94	70	23	19	164
Total	192	90	70	30	382

Source: Field survey (2023)

To calculate for expected frequency

$$Fe = \frac{\text{Row total} \times \text{Column total}}{\text{Grand Total}}$$

Grand Total

$$\text{Cell a} = \frac{218 \times 192}{382} = 109.8$$

$$\text{Cell b} = \frac{218 \times 90}{382} = 51.4$$

$$\text{Cell c} = \frac{218 \times 70}{382} = 39.9$$

$$\text{Cell d} = \frac{218 \times 30}{382} = 17.1$$

$$\text{Cell e} = \frac{164 \times 192}{382} = 82.4$$

$$\text{Cell f} = \frac{164 \times 90}{382} = 38.6$$

$$\text{Cell g} = \frac{164 \times 70}{382} = 30.1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cell h} &= \frac{164 \times 30}{382} \\ &= \mathbf{12.9} \end{aligned}$$

CHI-SQUARE DISTRIBUTION TABLE

Cell	fo	Fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$
A	98	109.8	-11.8	139.24	1.27
B	28	51.4	-23.4	547.56	10.65
C	47	39.9	7.1	50.41	1.26
d	11	17.1	-6.1	37.21	2.18
E	94	82.4	11.6	134.56	1.63
F	70	38.6	31.4	985.96	25.54
G	23	30.1	-7.1	50.41	1.67
H	19	12.9	6.1	37.22	2.89
					$\sum x^2 = 47.09$

Source: Field survey 2023

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (R-1)(C-1) \\ &= (2-1)(4-1) \\ &= 1 \times 3 \\ &= \mathbf{3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The level of significance} &= 0.05 \\ \text{Calculated value} &= 47.09 \\ \text{Critical table value} &= 7.8 \end{aligned}$$

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 47.09 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8 the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is found that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolises.

Discussion on Findings

Out of the three Hypotheses postulated in this study, only the first one was subjected to statistical test due to space constraint. Therefore, the finding of the study was also a result of the first hypothesis tested. Based on that premise, hypothesis one (1) was tested using question one (1) from the questionnaire and it found that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 50% strongly agreed that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis. This finding is in consonance with the findings of renowned authors, particularly Petermann et al. (2011), who averred that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in society. This led to accepting the alternate hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis that there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to recurrent power outages along Aba and Itu national grid.

5. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

The researchers were compelled by the recurrent power outages recently witnessed along Aba and Itu national grid that had thrown the entire metropolitan cities of Uyo and Eket, and their environs into total blackout thereby, impacting great negative implications on the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State as a whole.

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. A sample of 400 respondents was selected from a population of 1,329,000 indigenes and occupants of the Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities using confidence interval of 5 and confidence level of 95% (0.05). A well-developed Likert-type scale was used for data collection.

The instrument was validated and found to be reliable. It was personally administered by the researchers. The data collected were analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentage tables. The first hypothesis only was tested using the inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) at 0.05 level of significance. The results obtained showed that, there are implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses in Uyo and Eket metropolis.

Conclusion

After assessing the recurrent power outages recently witnessed along Aba and Itu national grid that had thrown the entire metropolitan cities of Uyo and Eket, and their environs blackout thereby, impacting great negative implications on the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State as a whole, and arising from the finding made from this study, the researchers came to the following conclusions: that the importance of the having steady power supply in the metropolitan cities of Uyo and Eket, and their environs cannot be overemphasized. PHED should be equipped to carry out effective and efficient service delivery to the people. The National Assembly should make legislations that are favourable to the smooth operations of PHED, while the Federal and State Government should provide favorable conditions that would enable company to carry out their functions effectively.

To achieve the foregoing, government should practically be involved in reducing the cost of production; availability of electric power; accessibility of credit facilities and funding; reduction of political interference and politicizing the processes, removal of multiple taxation outlets; maintaining policy agreements; eliminating policy somersaults; curtailing intimidation of private sector workers in privatized enterprises by government officials; providing public enlightenment for citizens and beneficiaries of services; maintain an efficient feedback mechanism to measure performance of privatized enterprises and their service delivery; and a proper balance between a maximized profit motive and a service delivery orientation of the privatized enterprise will go a long way in bringing to reality the benefits of efficient provision of services and value chain.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the single finding of this research, a recommendation was made thus: The Federal Government should accept the fact that there are gross negative implications of value chain on small and medium scale businesses as well as individuals in Uyo and Eket metropolis due to the incessant and recurrent power outages on the Aba and Itu National Grid. As such, federal government should equip and provide favorable conditions that would enable PHED to carry out effective and efficient service delivery to the people.

References

Akinboro, F.G.; Adejumobi, L.A., & Makinde, V. (2016). Solar energy installation in Nigeria: observations, prospect, problems and solution. *Transnational Journal of Science and Technology* 2(4), 73-84.

- Angel, G. (2012). The Emergence of Global Value Chains: What Do They Mean for Business. G20 Trade and Investment Promotion Summit. Mexico City: OECD. Retrieved 7 September 2013.
- Carreras, B. A.; Lynch, V. E.; Dobson, I., & Newman, D. E. (2002). Dynamics, criticality and self-organization in a model for blackouts in power transmission systems (pdf). Hawaii International Conference on Systems Sciences, January 2002, Hawaii. Archived from the original (PDF) on August 21, 2003.
- Carreras, B. A.; Lynch, V. E.; Newman, D. E., Dobson, I. (2003). "Blackout mitigation assessment in power transmission systems" (pdf). 36th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. Hawaii. Archived from the original(PDF) on April 1, 2011.
- Decision Support Tools (2013). Porter's Value Chain. Cambridge University: Institute for Manufacturing (IfM). Archived from the original on 29 October 2013. Retrieved 9 September 2013.
- Dobson, I., Chen, J., Thorp, J., Carreras, B., & Newman, D. (2002). Examining criticality of blackouts in power system models with cascading events. 35th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS'02), January 7-10, 2002. Big Island, Hawaii. Archived from the original on September 12, 2003. Retrieved August 17, 2003.
- Fowler, M. (1997). Historical Beginnings of Theories of Electricity and Magnetism. from http://galileoandstein.physics.virginia.edu/more_stuff/E&M_Hist.html.
- Home, R. (1972). Franklin's electrical atmospheres. *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 6 (2), 131-151.
- Kenton, W. (2019). Value chain. Investopedia. Retrieved 2019-02-20.
- Kovaleski, D. (2018). Senate hearing examines electric industry's ability to restore power after system-wide blackouts. *Daily Energy Insider*. Retrieved October 23, 2018.
- Michael, E. P. (1985). *Competitive advantage: creating and sustaining superior performance*. The Free Press.

Porter, M. E. (1985). *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York: Simon and Schuster. ISBN 9781416595847. Retrieved 9 September 2013.

Pierre, L., Stephen, M., & Kirsti, M. (2013). *The tax policy landscape five years after the crisis (report)*. OECD Taxation Working Papers. France: OECD. Archived from the original on 18 March 2014. Retrieved 7 September 2013.

Petermann, T., Bradke, H., Lüllmann, A., Poetzsch, M., & Riehm, U. (2011). *What happens during a blackout - consequences of a prolonged and wide-ranging power Outage*. Berlin: Office of Technology Assessment at the German Bundestag.

Rayport, J. F., & Sviokla, J. J. (2000). *Exploiting the Virtual Value Chain*. HBR, 1995(November-December), 75-85.

The Punch Newspaper. (25th May, 2015). *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research* ISSN 0973-4562 11(7) (2016), 4930-49330 Research India Publications.

Tricker, R. A. R. (1965). *Early Electrodynamics: The First Law of Circulation*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.

Udoh, S. U. (2014). *Public Administration and Development Studies: A Contemporary Perspective in Developing Economies*. Abuja: Nom Nom Publishers,